

Ethical Principles of Working with Laboratory Animals in Experimental Immunology

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Abstract: *In immunological research, laboratory animals are used to determine the possibility of immunotropic activity or immunotoxic effect of the studied drugs, for pre-clinical experimental study of new pharmacological substances.*

Key words: *experimental, diagnostic sera, nutrient media, animals.*

It is known that research methods with the involvement of laboratory animals are called biological or experimental (experimental) research, and animals involved in experimental research are called laboratory or experimental (experimental) animals [3].

Laboratory animals are also used as donors for the preparation of nutrient mediums for microbiological studies, for obtaining erythrocytes, blood plasma, and leukocytes, which are necessary for performing serological reactions. They also serve to diagnose some infectious diseases, to determine the virulence and toxigenicity of strains of microorganisms, the activity of vaccines and their safety [3].

Laboratory animals most commonly used in microbiological and immunological studies include albino rats, albino mice, rabbits, and guinea pigs.

Purebred rats are used in experimental studies to obtain blood, blood serum, erythrocytes, to model various infections (tuberculosis, tuberculosis, brucellosis, tetanus, diphtheria, gas gangrene) and toxicoinfections. White mice are used to determine the activity and safety of biological preparations (vaccines, therapeutic and diagnostic sera), to standardize biological preparations, to determine the activity and safety of antibacterial preparations, to model salmonellosis, botulism, tetanus, gas gangrene, as well as staphylococcal, streptococcal, pneumococcal, meningococcal infections. , immunological indicators - antibody-forming spleen and nucleus storage cells, thymus, bone marrow, lymph node cells in the small intestine, determination of the titer of antibodies against sheep erythrocytes in blood serum, hematological indicators - determination of erythrocytes and leukocytes in the blood, are used to form the model of "bacterial translocation phenomenon" [3, 7, 12].

Blood, serum and plasma of rabbits of different breeds, erythrocytes, hemolytic serum, obtaining antibacterial diagnostic sera, determining the activity of some vaccines and serum preparations, inducing allergic reactions, determining the virulence of staphylococci, tuberculosis, pseudotuberculosis, salmonellosis, tetanus, botulism, gas gangrene and rabbits dysentery, as well as staphylococcal, streptococcal, used to create a model of meningococcal infections. In the case of guinea pigs, obtaining blood, blood serum, complement, erythrocytes, inducing allergic reactions (anaphylaxis), experimentally determining the activity and safety of biological preparations (vaccines and serums), various infectious diseases (manga, tuberculosis, listeriosis, gas gangrene, tetanus, brucellosis , tularemia, salmonellosis, pertussis, rickettsiosis). used for [3, 12].

Purpose of work. To substantiate the importance of following the ethical principles of working with laboratory animals in experimental research involving laboratory animals in experimental microbiology and immunology.

Material and methods. Materials of experimental studies conducted with a total of 239 purebred mice and 80 purebred rats were used to achieve the goal. These studies were carried out in traditional ways.

Results obtained and discussion. The main principles of the rules for working with laboratory animals (care, use for scientific purposes) in the process of involving laboratory animals in experiments are as follows: improvement of methods of diagnosis, treatment and prevention of diseases, use of laboratory animals in medical-biological experimental studies aimed at determining the level of influence of various physical, chemical and biological factors on the body; justifying the benefit to the development of science and society. Also, the compassionate treatment of laboratory animals creates the basis for the formation of higher moral principles in research scientists and doctors.

We managed to perform microbiological and immunological experimental studies involving laboratory animals based on international regulations [2]. These regulations aim to coordinate the use of laboratory animals in medical and biological research. Compassion and rational use of experimental animals are the main principles of conducting these studies. Adherence to these principles increased the safety of the experiments while ensuring their effectiveness and reliability.

It was also appropriate that we worked within the framework of the regulations of the European Parliament on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes [9] when working with experimental animals.

In addition, the requirements and recommendations of the specially created "Guide" [11] for the care and use of laboratory animals, the recommendations of the Association [10] for special training of scientific and technical personnel working with laboratory animals were also fully taken into account.

We would like to acknowledge that, due to strict adherence to international biological safety regulations [5] required for working with experimental animals, there were absolutely no unpleasant situations among the staff during the experiments.

It is known that the three R concepts proposed by Russell and Birch in 1959 serve as the theoretical basis of the strategy for improving the condition of experimental animals: Refinement, Reduction, Replacement [8].

Due to the great theoretical and practical importance of this concept for microbiological and immunological experimental research, we found it necessary to explain these principles.

The principle of excellence refers to the humane treatment of laboratory animals in the preparation and conduct of experiments. The main requirement when working with experimental animals is to completely prevent or reduce to a very low amount (minimum) the pain, suffering and discomfort that the animals suffer. Based on this principle, the conditions of keeping laboratory animals should be suitable for their type and accepted requirements, therefore, they should always protect their health. The scientific worker who supervises and manages the care of animals must have experience working with this type of animals, the necessary qualifications and special training. A veterinarian should also be able to provide assistance when necessary [9]. Procedures that may cause pain and suffering in laboratory animals should be carried out with the help of adequate sedatives and painkillers. Surgical, traumatological and other painful operations and procedures cannot be performed on non-anesthetized animals. It is recommended to place a catheter in the central vein if the experimental procedure requires rapid blood collection from the laboratory animal and the introduction of drugs into its body many times.

If a laboratory animal is exposed to severe or chronic pain and suffering during an experiment and it is not possible to eliminate or reduce it, the animal should be euthanized after or during the experiment. The optimal and universal method of euthanasia is the deliberate administration of anesthesia (anesthetic) in a lethal dose. In experimental biology, killing laboratory animals by exposure to liquid nitrogen is also used.

The principle of substitution is based on the need to use advanced scientific technologies in place of laboratory animals in experiments whenever possible. Only if it is proved that it is impossible not to use laboratory animals in experiments, they can be involved in experiments. The type of laboratory animal needed to perform scientific work must be adequate for the purpose of the experiment being conducted. The possibility of using animals that are always at a lower stage of evolutionary development should be considered first. For example, there is a growing focus on testing on invertebrates.

The principle of minimization is to reduce the number of laboratory animals involved in experiments, that is, they should always be used in a minimum amount. At this point, we would like to point out that the number of animals involved in the experiment should be sufficient to obtain statistically reliable results, as long as it is minimal. This requires careful formulation of the step-by-step implementation of the planned experiment, using scientific resources from the experiment, preliminary results obtained in vitro, and computer modeling. As a basic problem of medical-biological experiments, the variability of individuals within one species can be solved by using animals that are genetically identical (belonging to the same line).

Conclusions.

1. Strict adherence to the internationally recognized rules of biological safety during experimental research in experimental microbiology and immunology increases the reliability, efficiency and safety of experiments.
2. Organizing and conducting experiments based on the ethical principles of working with laboratory animals allows to treat animals with compassion and save funds allocated for scientific work.
3. Compliance with the ethical principles of working with laboratory animals and the rules of biological safety will increase the scientific culture of employees along with the international recognition of the results of scientific work.

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